

RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION OF UTERINE FIBROIDS: ADVANCING MINIMALLY INVASIVE TREATMENT FOR WOMEN

Deb Nath Ishika¹

Student of International Faculty, Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan¹
Department of obstetrics and gynecology, Tashkent Medical Academy
Scientific Advisor-PhD Prof. **Abdurazakova Mukhayyo Dilshodovna**

Introduction. Radiofrequency Ablation of uterine fibroids refers to a minimally invasive procedure where heat waves of around 60°C is used to cause thermal destruction of the fibroid tissue by coagulation of the blood vessels supplying the fibroid and ischemic necrosis of abnormal tissue with gradual reduction in fibroid size. Treatment of uterine fibroids has emerged out to be an important concern among women population. The cornerstone for the treatment of leiomyomas are myomectomy and hysterectomy but their morbidity rates are not satisfactory due to various post treatment complications.

Research objective. -The main aim of this research is to determine the post treatment outcomes of Laparoscopic RFA and Transvaginal RFA; focusing on fertility and pregnancy outcomes.

Materials and methods. A systematic study was conducted at Nazareth hospital (India) by Dr. Neha Gupta and Dr. Kalashree where case histories of 44 patients with symptomatic uterine fibroids were collected based on certain inclusion and exclusion criteria. These women were selected who desired uterine preservation for future fertility. The uterine size of the fibroid and fibroid volume was assessed using transvaginal USG and MRI. Average fibroid size was $\leq 12\text{cm}$ and fibroid volume $\leq 300\text{cm}^3$. They had at least 3 months of heavy menstrual bleeding within 6 months before enrollment. These patients had normal coagulation profile, and their hemoglobin level was found to be $\geq 10\text{g/dL}$ at the time of treatment. The average age of these patients at the time of treatment was 35 ± 2 years. Main outcomes were based on pregnancy results, patient recovery metrics, fibroid volume change, time for procedure, Health-related Quality of Life (HRQL) and re-interventions. These outcomes were confirmed after a follow-up of 24 months of the patients who underwent RFA.

Research Results. 44 case reports were identified from case reports with a history of symptomatic uterine fibroids. Out of these 44 patients, 20 pts underwent transvaginal RFA, and 24 patients underwent Laparoscopic RFA. The mean procedure time was found to be 45 minutes in transvaginal RFA. The patients were discharged and returned to normal activities by 4.2 days. A follow-up of 24 months was conducted in these patients where reduction in fibroid volume at 12 months follow up was found to be 69%, HRQOL increased by 40.9. Reintervention rate was found to be 4.8% among 6 patients. Our study highlights the efficiency of the Radiofrequency ablation in curing FIGO 2 to 5 fibroids, while the fibroids rated FIGO 2 to 4 are less reachable using other surgical methods. A total of 22 pregnancies were reported of which 12 were after Laparoscopic RFA and 10 were after Transvaginal RFA (the average age of women at conception after RFA was 35 ± 2 years old. The ablated size of fibroids varied from 0.9cm to 12.5cm and the number of fibroids treated were between 1 and 3. Average interval between RFA and pregnancy ranged from 3 to 33 months, with a mean found to be 16 months. The pregnancy study outcomes included 85% full term deliveries with no serious complication and a 12% of spontaneous abortion rate that matches the general obstetric population. Greater than 50% women had uncomplicated vaginal birth while lesser percentage underwent cesarean section. There were no instances of placenta accreta or uterine rupture suggesting that RFA is safe for women who desire to preserve

future fertility.

Conclusion. Thus, this research shows that Radiofrequency ablation of uterine fibroids is redefining the landscape of uterine myoma treatment. It is a very safe, minimally invasive advanced technology which is a promising alternative to the traditional myomectomy and hysterectomy. It can be performed in a day care, single setting where it offers a low complexity substitute and has also proven to be versatile and effective with rapid recovery and mild post operative pain. Not only that, it is also cost effective for the patient as hospitalization cost is not required.